

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
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MUNDARIJA

Organizational Behavior and Leadership.....	10
Ibrokhim Gulomov	
Baliqchilikda klasterlarini tashkil etishning nazariy asoslari	18
Olim Murtazayev, Muydinov Olim Bekmurotovich	
Оценка состояния привлечения инвестиций в сферу туризма Узбекистана и механизмы управления	24
Арзиматов Бобирмирзо Зокирджон угли	
Biologik aktivlar buxgalteriya hisobni milliy va xalqaro standartlarga muvofiq takomillashtirish masalalari ...	27
Axmadaliyeva Zebo Abduxalimovna	
Aholi yashash joylarida yong'in risklarini bartaraf etish xizmatlardan foydalanish imkoniyatlari	32
Aziz Zikriyoev	
O'zbekistonda ilmiy darajali kadrlar tayyorlash tizimi boshqaruvining tashkiliy tuzilmasi va vazifalari.....	40
Beknaeva Shaxnoza Vladimirovna	
Mintaqaviy turizmning iqtisodiyot rivojlanishiga ta'siri (O'zbekiston turistik xizmatlar bozori misolida).....	45
D. B. O'roqova	
Qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlarini ko'paytirishning asosiy yo'llari.....	50
Ibrohimov Boburmirzo Baxtiyor o'g'li, Sayfiddinov Sarvarbek Anvarbek o'g'li	
Sanoat korxonalarining aksiyalar bozorida faoliyati tahlili: muammolar va yechimlar	55
Igitov Jurabek Kuzibekovich	
Qurilishda modernizatsiya va diversifikatsiya qilish asosida yangi ishlab chiqarish quvvatlarini oshirish	63
Islamov Ozodjon	
Sanoat korxonalarini innovatsion salohiyatini oshirishning tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmini takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	67
J. K. Boymurodov	
Mamlakatda yashil iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirish yo'nalishlari	72
Kadirxodjayeva Nilufar Raxmatullayevna	
BlokchEYn texnologiyalari yordamida raqamli iqtisodiyotni o'zgartirish	77
Karabayev Rustam Zafarovich, Saitkamolov Muxammadxo'ja Sobirxo'ja o'g'li	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida zamonaviy mehnat bozorining rivojlanishi	84
Layli Mirzayeva	
Xizmat ko'rsatish sohasini rivojlantirishda investitsion resurslardan samarali foydalanish mexanizmlari.....	88
Luiza Komilovna Xaydarova	
Umumta'lim muassasalari sonining ekonometrik tahlilini pedagogik metodlar yordamida amalga oshirish....	93
Ravshanova Muhayyo Maxmanazarovna	
O'zbekiston tarixiy shaharlarida turistik faoliyati shakllanishi va ularni boshqarishning nazariy asoslari.....	98
Meliqulov G'ayrat Abdug'afforovich	
Iqtisodiy rivojlanish va ilmiy tadqiqot rivojlanishining havo ifloslanish darajasiga ta'siri	105
Murodullayev Kamoliddin Sherzod o'g'li, Sadibekova Bibisora Djapparovna, Turdiqulov Farrux Ravshanjon o'g'li	
Hududlarni rivojlantirish va "yashil iqtisodiyot"ni shakllantirishning ekologik muammolari.....	110
Maxkamov Saidafzal Saidkamol o'g'li, Yigitaliyeva Dilnavo Mansurjon qizi	
Ekoturizm obyektining tasniflanishi va alohida xususiyatlari	116
Qodirov Azizjon Anvarovich	
Mamlakatimiz oliy ta'lim tizimida sifat menejmentidan foydalanishning konseptual asoslari	121
Saidqulova Furuza Farmonovna	
Bo'lajak iqtisodchilarning kasbiy kompetensiyalari.....	125
Shukurova Marifat Xodjiakbar qizi	
Ta'limning bosqichlari va ularning inson kapitalini shakllantirishdagi ahamiyati	129
To'rayeva Hurriyat To'yqulovna	

Hududlarda to'g'ridan to'g'ri xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb etish dasturini amalga oshirishda marketingni rivojlantirish yo'llari	136
Xamidov O. X., Tojiyeva A. F.	
Investitsiyalar marketingining strategik aspektlari.....	143
Xodjamberdiyeva Dilnoza Bahtiyorovna	
Xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb etishda investitsion muhit jozibadorligini oshirishga nazariy qarashlar	149
A. Bektemirov, A. A. Abdurahmonov	
Qishloq xo'jaligi raqobatbardoshligini oshirishning ilg'or xorij tajribasi.....	154
Abdulloyev Asliddin Junaydullayevich, Ochilov Narzullo Fayzulloyevich	
Sanoat ishlab chiqarish tizimining investitsion xususiyatlari.....	159
Yodgorova Xalima To'liqinovna	
Turizm sohasi uchun yuqori malakali kadrlarni tayyorlashda davlat va xususiy sherikchilikning o'zaro bog'liqligi tahlili.....	165
Raxmatov Adxam Itolmasovich	
Mamlakatimizda turizm tashkilotlari faoliyatini qo'llab-quvvatlash maqsadida marketing instrumentlari orqali samarali tizim yaratish.....	169
Suyunova Kamilla Baxromovna	
Qishloq xo'jaligida agrokimyo xizmatlar ko'rsatishning iqtisodiy samaradorligini oshirish yo'llari	173
Tabayev Azamat Zaripbayevich	
Yashil iqtisodiyotga investitsiyalarni jalb qilishni faollashtirish muammolari.....	178
Xomitov K. Z., Masharipova S. R.	
Considerations on the Problem of Illegal Migration and Human Trafficking	183
Azamatova Gulmira Bayirbekovna, Otarbayeva Guljan Kobeyevna	
Sustainable Development and Environmental Economics in Uzbekistan: A Focus on Carbon Pricing and Renewable Energy	186
Muhammadiyev Po'latjon Ilhomjon o'g'li, Urganbayeva Dilnoza Toxtasinovna	
The use of Digital Technologies in the Provision Of Utilities to the Population	192
Mamanazarov Oybek Shomurodovich, Inoyatova Durdona Shoxaydarovna, Alijonov Jamshid Alijon o'g'li	
The Current State of the Digital Economy in the Agrarian Sphere: Problems and Solutions	196
Babadjanov Abdirashid Musayevich	
Behavioral Theory of the Firm.....	201
Egamberdiyeva Oydin Abror qizi	
The Role of Information Technologies in Increasing the Capitalization of Commercial Banks	207
Egamova Makhfurat Esanovna	
Финансовые риски в исламском финансировании для внедрения в Республики Узбекистан	211
Абдуллоев Фуркат Олимджонович	
Совершенствование методологии экспертизы инвестиционных проектов	216
Бекимбетова Гулнора Маратовна	
Методические подходы к формированию механизмов стратегического управления развитием химической отрасли.....	223
Бибутова Шахло Саъдуллаевна	
Меры по снижению доли теневой экономики в стране.....	228
Махмудова Юлдузхон Бахромжон кизи, Сафаров Гиёсиддин Абдуллаевич ўгли	
Формирование национальной инновационной системы – одна из приоритетных задач повышения конкурентоспособности Республики Узбекистан	232
Н. М. Махмудов, А. А. Алиев, З. А. Мирзоев	
Мониторинг и анализ современного состояния и развития промышленности в Узбекистане.....	237
Назарова Раъно Рустамовна, Исмоилова Малика Дилшодовна	
Цифровая платформа как инструмент трансформации бизнес-процессов.....	243
Раупов Жамшид Рашидович	
Роль применения ключевых показателей эффективности труда на предприятиях.....	249
Рахматуллаева Шахноза Хамидовна	

Влияние цифровой трансформации на инвестиционную привлекательность Узбекистана.....	255
Саиткамоллов Муҳаммадхожа Сабирходжа угли, Маркабаева Жансая Айбек кызы	
Организация и координация методической помощи при управлении педагогическими кадрами	261
Хакимова Майя Юрьевна	
Интеграция узбекистана в мировое экономическое содружество путем унификации бухгалтерского учета на основе МСФО	266
Зарипова Саёхат Зафаровна	
Tijorat banklari tomonidan investitsiya loyihalarini moliyalashni rivojlantirish imkoniyatlari.....	271
Abduqodirova Ozoda Anvarjon qizi	
Tijorat banklari tomonidan jismoniy shaxslarga ajratilgan kreditlarning joriy tahlili.....	276
Abdusalomov Jaxongir O'ktam o'g'li	
Globalashuv sharoitida mamlakatimizda sug'urta bozorini raqamlashtirishning ahamiyati	282
Anvarova Z.	
The Role of Parents and Teachers in Promoting a Healthy Lifestyle in Children.....	286
Axtamov Djamshed Baxromovich	
A Study of the Importance of Green Economy in Uzbekistan Sustainable Economic Development and its Measurement Indicators in Relation to Environment.....	291
Ataniyazova Maksuda Baltayevna, Tairova Zarnigor Mammot qizi	
Konsolidatsiyalashgan moliyaviy hisobot tuzishning zarurligi.....	296
Avazov Iloxom Ravshanovich	
Foydani soliqqa tortish obyekti sifatidagi iqtisodiy tarkibi.....	301
Axrorov Zarif Oripovich	
Surxondaryo viloyatida aholining uy-joy bilan ta'minlanganlik darajasini tahlili.....	309
Ibragimov Qobil To'xtamishovich	
Review of Methodological Approaches to Enterprises Financial Condition Analysis.....	314
Ismailova Maxbuba Mirxalilovna	
Innovatsion rivojlanish sharoitida xizmat ko'rsatish sohasini tasniflanishining nazariy va ilmiy asoslari.....	319
Masharipova Manzura Alimbayevna	
Korxonalarda benchmarking strategiyalarini qo'llashning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy mexanizmlari.....	325
Narziyeva Dilafiruz Muxtorovna	
Davlat budjetining soliqsiz daromadlari shakllanishini takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	330
O'ktamova Nargiza Narzulla qizi	
Mamlakatimizda sanoat ishlab chiqarishi korxonalarining rivojlanish holati tahlili.....	334
Olimov Maqsudjon Komiljon o'g'li	
Moliyaviy natijalar to'g'risidagi hisobotni moliyaviy hisobotning xalqaro standartlar talablari asosida tuzish.....	339
Pardayeva Zulfizar Alimovna	
Raqamlashtirish sharoitida qo'shma korxonasi faoliyatining tahlili.....	343
Rashidov Jamshid Xamidovich	
Kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikning rivojlanishida oilaviy tadbirkorlikning o'rni.....	348
Raximov Baxromjon Ibroximovich, Saloxiddinov Zuxriddin Nuriddin o'g'li	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida xizmat ko'rsatishning ilmiy asoslari.....	352
Suyunov Asror Baxtiyorovich	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida telekommunikatsiya sohasini rivojlantirish ilmiy asoslari.....	356
Toshmatov Salohiddin Zayniddinovich	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida innovatsiyalarni joriy etishning huquqiy masalalari.....	360
Turg'unov Saloxiddin Jamol o'g'li, Mirzayeva Mohidil Vohidovna	
Zamonaviy sharoitlarda korxonalarining moliyaviy baqarorligini yaxshilash masalalari	366
Usmanova Guljahon Ulug'bek qizi	
Franshizalarni jalb qilishda davlat boshqaruvi tizimida marketing tadqiqotlarining ahamiyati	371
Xodjayev Anvar Rasulovich	

Transport Decarbonization Strategy.....	377
Yarashova Vasila Kamalovna, Muradov Bekzod Xidirnazar ugli	
Temir yo'l transportida ishlab chiqarish faoliyatining iqtisodiy samaradorligini oshirish	382
Yermatova Dilnoza Axmadjonovna	
Iqtisodiyotda davlat ishtirokini qisqartirish va xususiy tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirish istiqbollari	387
Yuldashev Xusniddin Abdullayevich	
Issiqlik ta'minoti xizmatlarini ko'rsatish samaradorligi va sifatini baholash ko'rsatkichlari tizimi.....	390
Abdulaziz Abdumo'minovich Matro'ziyev	
Issiqlik ta'minoti xizmatlari sifatiga ta'sir etuvchi omillar va ularni baholash	394
Abdulaziz Abdumo'minovich Matro'ziyev	
Jismoniy shaxslarning mol-mulkiga soliq solishni takomillashtirish.....	399
Abdullayev Zafarjon Alijonovich, Zaydullayev Abduhabib Boliqul o'g'li	
Sug'urta tashkilotlarida hisob siyosatini ishlab chiqishning ahamiyati.....	404
Abduraimova Maftunaxon Axmatovna	
Bank risklarini boshqarishning xalqaro tajribalari.....	409
Abdurasulov Jaxongir Abduvaliyevich	
Tadbirkorlik subyektlari ijtimoiy ma'sulligini ta'minlash mexanizmining amal qilish darajasi.....	416
Bayisbayev Javlon Nurlanovich	
Qishloq aholisining qishloq xo'jaligida bilim va innovatsiyalarni o'zlashtirishga ta'sir etuvchi omillarni iqtisodiy baholash (Samarqand viloyati misolida).....	421
Bozorova Lobar Nuralevna	
Направления совершенствования инновационных стратегий в деятельности промышленных предприятий.....	427
Дониерова Зухрабону Алишер кизи	
Mol-mulk solig'ining korxonalar faoliyatiga ta'siri.....	432
Qudiyarov Kishibay Ramatullayevich	
Banklar reytingini aniqlash va barqarorligini ta'minlashning ustuvor yo'nalishlari.....	438
Maxmudov Omon Tuxtayevich	
Iqtisodiyotni modernizatsiyalash sharoitida tijorat banklarining aktiv va passiv operatsiyalarini innovatsion usullar orqali boshqarishni takomillashtirish	442
Mo'minova Ma'suda Baxtiyarovna	
Auditorlik tekshiruvini dasturiy ta'minot asosida tashkil etish: muammo va yechimlar.....	447
Nazarova Kamola Sattoral qizi	
Ishlab chiqarish infratuzilmasini rivojlantirishning davlat tomonidan tartibga solish konsepsiyasi.....	453
Normurodov Xusan Eshmaxmatovich	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikning ahamiyati hamda uni rivojlantirish istiqbollari.....	460
Nurullayeva Shaxnoza, Saydullayeva Saodat	
Tijorat banklari inson kapitali samaradorligini baholashda KPI ko'rsatkichlaridan foydalanish mexanizmlari	467
Turaeva Mastura Kurbanovna	
Сущность и особенности инвестиционно-строительного процесса	471
А. Бектемиров, Б.М.Абдувалиев	
Tijorat banklarida muammoli kreditlarni boshqarishning dolzarb masalalari.....	478
Saidov Hayotjon Raxmatulloevich	
Tijorat banklarida kredit operatsiyalari hisobini takomillashtirish.....	482
Sa'dullayeva Asalxon Muzaffarovna	
Ko'p tarmoqli fermer xo'jaliklarining raqobatbardoshlikni baholash usullari	485
Abdulloyev Asliddin Junaydullayevich, Teshayev Mirolim Djumayevich	
Tadbirkorlik subyektlarida soliq yukini optimallashtirish mexanizmi	490
To'xsanov Quدراتillo Nozimovich	

Davlat sektorida ichki audit tadbirlarini umumiy rejalashtirish	495
Xamidova Z. U.	
Aholi moliyaviy savodxonligini oshirish va uning ahamiyati.....	501
Xudayarova Xurshida Abdunazarovna	
Kambag'allikni qisqartirishning xorijiy mamlakatlar tajribasi.....	505
Xudoyberdiyev Jamshid Juraboy o'g'li	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida buxgalteriya hisobi va ichki auditni takomillashtirish	511
Shaymatova Nargiza Ashurovna	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida sug'urta xizmatlari.....	516
Shodmonova Odina G'ofur qizi	
Fuqarolar davlat pensiya ta'minoti tizimining amaldagi holati tahlili.....	520
Sholdarov Dilshod Azimiddin o'g'li	
Aholiga bank xizmatlari ko'rsatishning ijtimoiy ahamiyati.....	525
Eldor Uskanov	
Innovatsion boshqaruvning ilg'or xorijiy tajribalari	530
Yusupova Jamila Karamatdinovna	
Neft-gaz korxonalarini moliyaviy-iqtisodiy faoliyati natijalari tahlili ("O'ZBEKNEFTGAZ" AJ misolida)	534
Umurzoqov Jamoliddin Sherbekovich	
Korxonalarda savdo marketing faoliyati samaradorligini baholash.....	541
Sobirov Azizbek Avzbekovich	
Moliyaviy firibgarliklarga qarshi kurashishda raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish imkoniyatlari.....	548
Gadaev Ismat Yadgarovich	
Hududlarda islom iqtisodiyoti tamoyillari asosida amalga oshirilgan investitsion loyihalar: to'siqlar va yechimlar	551
Irgasheva Gulbahor Sodiqovna	
O'zbekistonda investitsiyalardan samarali foydalanish asosida oziq-ovqat sanoati samaradorligini oshirish yo'llari.....	554
Kobilova Nasiba Xurramovna	
Foreign Economic Relations as a Factor of Effective Functioning of the Economy	561
Bakhodurova Sulkhya Azizkhodjaevna, Li Marina Rudolfovna, Mukhtarova Donata Ravshanbekovna, Romashkin Roman Anatolyevich	
Modern Approaches to the Organization and Development of the Consumer Services Market.....	566
Musyeva Shoira Azimovna	
Ishlab chiqarish siklini qisqartirishning iqtisodiy samaradorligi.....	570
Odina Nabiyevna Tuychiyeva, Nazarova Latofat Toirjon qizi	
Asalarichilik mahsulotlari bozorida marketing strategiyasini amalga oshirish.....	575
Rashidova Xadicha Tursunalievna	
Iqtisodiyotni modernizatsiyalash sharoitida bank faoliyatini iqtisodiy-matematik modellashtirish yo'llari	581
Raxmanov Mexridin Sindarovich	
Korporativ boshqaruv amaliyoti bo'yicha hisobot tuzish bo'yicha xorijiy tajriba.....	586
Tashmatov Rustam Xusanovich	
Iqtisodiyotda davlat ishtirokini qisqartirish va xususiy tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirish istiqbollari	592
Yuldashev Xusniddin Abdullayevich	
Iqtisodiyotda turizm o'rnini statistik baholash uslubiyoti.....	595
Zilola Jumanova	
Финансовые риски в исламском финансировании для внедрения в Республики Узбекистан	602
Абдуллоев Фуркат Олимджонович	
Блокчейн-технология и информационная безопасность в цифровой экономике Узбекистана.....	607
Кадиров Алишер Исмаилович	
Цифровая платформа как инструмент трансформации бизнес-процессов	611
Раупов Жамшид Рашидович	

O'zbekistonda zamonaviy kabel va sim mahsulotlari ishlab chiqaruvchi korxonalar faoliyatiga nazar.....	617
Rashidova Odina Olimjon qizi	
Современные тенденции развития валютных отношений в Узбекистане	622
Камалов Камолалдин Кахрамонович	
Sug'urta sohasining O'zbekiston iqtisodiyotidagi o'rni	626
Sharobiddinov Akramjon Goyibbayevich	
Kichik biznes va tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirishning xorij tajribasi va undan O'zbekistonda foydalanish yo'nalishlari	630
Fayziyeva Aziza Azamat qizi	
Modeling the Stackelberg strategy in a linear model (linear city) Hotteling.....	635
Musayeva Shaira Azimovna, Usmonova Dilfuza Ilkhomovna	
Mulkning kapitallashuvi darajasini iqtisodiy jihatdan amalga oshirish samaradorligini baholash uslublari.....	644
Norboyev Odil Abrayevich	
Tijorat banklarining kredit portfelini amaliy holati va ekonometrik tahlillari: ATB "Aloqabank" misolida.....	649
Norov Akmal Ruzimamatovich, Norova Nozima Nabiyeвна	
O'zbekistonda "yashil iqtisodiyot" muhitida kreditlash va moliyalashtirish imkoniyatlari	654
Taxir Urkinbayev	
Budjet tashkilotlarida ichki nazorat tizimini tashkil qilishning xususiyatlari.....	658
Abduraxmanov Ramazon Abdullayevich	
Chinese Commercial Banks Experience in Asset Diversification	663
Uktamova Nozima Narzulla kizi	
Sanoat taraqqiyotida ishlab chiqarish korxonalarini ustuvor rivojlantirish istiqbollari.....	667
Yadgarov Akram Akbarovich	
Анализ деятельности коммерческих банков Узбекистана по кредитованию физических лиц.....	673
Базарова Нигора Равшановна	
Mahalliy va xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb etishning innovatsion jarayonlarga ta'sirini baholash.....	684
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida innovatsiyalarning iqtisodiy samaradorligini oshirish yo'llari	689
Kuziyeva Nargiza Ramazanovna, Xusanov Faxriddin Jamoliddin o'g'li	
Tashqi mehnat migratsiyasi.....	694
O. N. Djurayev	
Raqamli iqtisodiyotda sanoat tarmog'ining davlat tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlanishini baholash	699
Otaboyeva Dildora	
Nobank kredit tashkilotlarining moliyaviy xizmatlari sifatini oshirishning xorijiy mamlakatlar tajribasi	705
Raimov Xurshid Muxtorovich	
Tijorat banklarida moliyaviy injiniringni qo'llash istiqbollari	711
Saipnazarov Sherbek Shaylavbekovich	
O'zbekiston Respublikasi moliya bozorida tijorat banklari faoliyati: muammo va yechimlar	716
Toymuxamedov Ibroxim Rixsiboevich, Jumaev Islombek Akram o'g'li	
Agrar ta'lim tizimida boshqaruv samaradorligini oshirish yo'llari	723
Boltayev Nurali Shiramatovich, Beglayev Uchqun Xurramovich, Abdiyev Izzat Risqiboyevich	
O'zini o'zi band qilgan shaxslardan olinadigan soliqlarni takomillashtirish orqali yashirin iqtisodiyotni jilovlash masalalari	731
Davranov Iskandar Jumayevich	
Iqtisodiy konsentratsiyalarni tartibga solish va nazorat qilishni takomillashtirish.....	738
Luqmanov Sharifxon A'zam o'g'li	
Role of Private and Public Kindergartens in Early Childhood Development	744
Makhmudova Munisakhon Abbos qizi	
"Yashil" enegriya quvvatlarini barpo etish iqtisodiy barqarorlikni ta'minlash asosi sifatida.....	749
Muminova Elnoraxon Abdukarimovna, Umarova Dilnoza Oybek qizi	
Xo'jalik yurituvchi subyektlarda CVP-tahlilni tashkil etishning muammoli jihatlari	754
Qlichev Baxtiyor Pardayevich	

Korxonada likvidlik riskini minimallashtirish orqali uning moliyaviy barqarorligini saqlab qolish	759
Latipova Shaxnoza Maxmudovna	
Развитие международных торгово-экономических связей Республики Узбекистан	766
Ким Татьяна Валерьевна, Гофуржонова Шахрибону Бахромжон кизи	
Kapital qurilishni boshqarish samaradorligini oshirishning dolzarb masalalari	774
A. Bektemirov, M. U. Sarimsoqov	
O'zbekiston mehnat bozorida yoshlarning ish bilan bandlik darajasini oshirish.....	780
Mambetjanov Qahramon Qurbandurdiyevich, Bahromov Shahzod Fazliddinovich	
Роль имиджа в улучшении инвестиционной привлекательности высших учебных заведений.....	787
Жанзаков Бекзот, Жонузоков Мирзабек	
Innovatsion kichik tadbirkorlikni qo'llab-quvvatlash bo'yicha xorij tajribasi va uni mamlakat iqtisodiyotida qo'llash imkoniyati.....	795
Toshaliyeva Saodat Toxirovna, Eshqulova Dilorom Abduravupovna	
Перспективы развития банковского сектора в Узбекистане для иностранных туристов	802
Муминов Шахзод Низомиддинович, Каримова Азиза Махомадризоевна	
Innovatsion faoliyat moliyaviy modellari va mexanizmlarini rivojlantirishning konseptual asoslari	806
Ruzibayeva Nargiza Xakimovna	
Qishloq xo'jaligi tarmoqlarini innovatsion rivojlantirish bo'yicha xorijiy tajribalar va ulardan respublikamizda samarali foydalanish yo'llari	814
Ishniyazov Baxrom Normamatovich	
Turistik xizmatlarining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari va marketing tadqiqotlari.....	819
Berdiqulova Iroda Rayimqulovna	
Qoraqalpog'iston qishloq xo'jaligi: asosiy muammolar va rivojlanishining ustuvor yo'nalishlari	823
Yeshimbetov Uktamjon Xudaybergenovich	
Iqtisodiyotning erkinlashtirilishi sharoitlarida kichik biznes sektori rivojlanishining imkoniyatlari.....	832
Botirova R. A., Sirojiddinov I. Q.	
Kriptoalyuta va blokcheyn tadqiqotlari: tendensiyalar va istiqbollar	835
Berdiqulov Jurabek	
Bank risklarni monitoring qilish tizimini takomillashtirish	837
Hamroyev Sherzod Axtamovich	
O'zbekiston hududlariga xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb qilishda ko'p qavatli "yashil" fermer xo'jaliklarini tashkil etishning ahamiyati	843
Turdimuratova Aziza Alisherovna	
Surxondaryo viloyatining mahalliy budjet daromadlarini oshirish yo'llari va uni arima modeli asosida prognozlash.....	846
Abdunazarova Shahnoza Norqo'chqor qizi	
Qishloq xo'jaligi tarmog'ining mamlakat iqtisodiyotidagi o'rni va undagi tarkibiy o'zgarishlarni statistik baholash.....	856
Zakirova Umida Maxamadaminovna	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida xizmat ko'rsatish korxonalarining ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy mohiyati	863
Pardayev Jamshid Muzaffarovich	
Turizm bozorini rivojlantirishda mehnat bozorining tutgan o'rni va ahamiyati	872
Berdiqulova Iroda Rayimqulovna, Berdikulov Jurabek	
Проблемы расчета определения и планирования прибыли предприятий в условиях модернизации экономики	876
Алиева С.С.	

A STUDY OF THE IMPORTANCE OF GREEN ECONOMY IN UZBEKISTAN SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT AND ITS MEASUREMENT INDICATORS IN RELATION TO ENVIRONMENT

TARAQQIYOT PROGRESS
ПРОГРЕСС

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Abstract: In this article, the need to use the green economy in order to achieve sustainable economic development of Uzbekistan, as well as the system of environmental indicators analyzing its condition, is researched.

Key words: Green economy, green sectors, green infrastructure, green jobs, environment, resource, external environment, CO₂.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada O'zbekiston barqaror iqtisodiy rivojlanishga erishish yo'lida yashil iqtisodiyotdan foydalanish zaruriyati hamda uning holatini tahlil qiluvchi ekologik ko'rsatkichlar tizimi tadqiq qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: Yashil iqtisodiyot, yashil sektorlar, yashil infratuzilma, yashil ish o'rinlari, atrof muhit, resurs, kimyoviy, chiqindilar, CO₂.

Аннотация: В данной статье исследуется необходимость использования зеленой экономики для достижения устойчивого экономического развития Узбекистана, а также система экологических показателей, анализирующих ее состояние.

Ключевые слова: Зеленая экономика, зеленые сектора, зеленая инфраструктура, зеленые рабочие места, окружающая среда, ресурсы, внешняя среда, CO₂.

INTRODUCTION

Green economy is the most modern field of knowledge today. Currently, in difficult economic situations, the green economy is an important factor in the stable economic development of countries. The green economy creates new and very wide opportunities for countries to achieve sustainable economic development. In this case, countries will have opportunities to become more competitive in the ecologically fresh world by integrating their existing industrial structures with the opportunities offered by the green economy. It is necessary for countries to effectively use the development potentials of the green economy that they have. In addition, the alarming indicators in today's ecosystem encourage countries to develop green. Therefore, the integration of the country's ability to competitively export complex green products by creating comprehensive sets of green products for domestic and foreign markets and relying on the methods of economic sophistication is an urgent task in the economic development of countries today.

Like many countries of the world, the need to transition to a green economy in our country is increasing day by day. In addition, in recent years, the rapid development of production processes in our country, the depletion of natural resources, and the increase in the population increase the demand for the transition to green economic development. For this reason, on November 4, 2019, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev adopted a decision on "Approving the strategy of the transition to the "green" economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the period of 2019–2030".. In this regard, the priority directions for improving the energy efficiency of the basic sectors of our country's economy were determined in the following areas ^[1]:

- In the field of electric energy;
- In the field of heat energy;
- In the field of oil and gas industry;
- In the field of chemical industry.

In addition, in order to bring the country's economy to a new stage of development, the "Uzbekistan–2030" strategy, which was developed on the basis of public discussion, also defined the urgent tasks of developing the green economy in our country. The 51st goal of our strategy was called "Transition to the "Green Economy", dramatically increasing the indicators of the use of renewable energy, which is its basis." The following tasks are defined in the strategy ^[2]:

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this research work, we studied the definitions of the term green economy given by international organizations. In addition, the need for the development of the green economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan has been revealed. Necessary proposals for the development of the green economy are given.

Literature review. There is no single clear definition of the green economy. However, we will consider the definitions accepted by the majority. For this, we referred to the manuals published by the following organizations:

- Global Green New Deal,
- OECD,
- United Nations Environmental Program,
- World Bank,
- Global Green Growth Institute,
- European Environmental Agency.

Table 3: Definition to "green economy" by some International organizations ^[3]

The introducing entity	Characteristics and definitions
Global Green New Deal 2009	The economic crisis provides the opportunity to introduce a global green new deal, which consists in stimulating the economy towards the development of green sectors, green infrastructure and green jobs. A greening infrastructure is a process of transforming a business activity such that it reduces emissions of greenhouse gases and consumption of resources, produces less waste, and reduces social inequalities at the same time, ensuring the return on natural, human and economic capital.

OECD 2010	“Green growth” means striving for economic growth and development, simultaneously preventing environmental degradation, biodiversity loss and the unsustainable use of natural resources. “Green growth” means separating the effects of a business activity from the effects of an environmental activity, as well as striving for investment in the environment to be the driving force of economic growth.
World Bank 2012	Green growth is an effective growth in terms of using clean resources, i.e. reducing pollution and environmental degradation, resistant to natural hazards and using environmental management to prevent other disasters
Global Green Growth Institute 2012	Green growth is the new revolutionary development paradigm that sustains economic growth while at the same time ensuring climate and environmental sustainability. It is aimed at reducing poverty, creating jobs, social integration and the sustainability of ecosystems, alleviating climate changes, supporting biodiversity, and providing access to clean energy and water.
UNEP 2011	A green economy is one that has a positive influence on people’s well-being and social equity, while reducing environmental risk and the consumption of natural resources.
European Environmental Agency 2012	Green economy is an economy where environmental, economic and social policies and innovations support societies in the effective use of resources, while at the same time improving human well-being, accentuating social integration and protecting the natural systems which sustain life on the Earth

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Over the past decade, the green economy has been seen as an important policy framework for sustainable development in both developed and developing countries. In addition, the importance of developing green economy in our country is increasing day by day. For example, the need to transition to a green economy was emphasized at the president’s meeting on the field of ecology on April 29 of this year. According to statistiks, more than 22,000 industrial enterprises have been launched and more than 250,000 houses have been built in our country from 2020 to the present. over a ton represents the need to develop a green economy ^[4].

Based on the official data of the Agency of Statistiks, we can say that the amount of pollutants released into the atmosphere has not fallen below the limit of 700,000 since 2010. By 2023, almost 800 thousand-1 million. Organized in the ton interval. By 2023, pollution has returned to a record level. This indicator is more than 2 times higher than in 2022.

Figure 1: Pollutants released into the atmosphere (thousand tons)^[5]

In addition, problems of using water resources are emerging in the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as in Central Asian countries. The information in the table below also shows that it is necessary to accelerate the establishment of economic development that preserves nature.

Table 1: Analysis of some statistical indicators of our country (mln.m³)¹

	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Water resources	58918.31	51002.74	53975.86	51217.17	43661.6	44487.6	45961.5
Permanent population	32120.5	32656.7	33255.5	33905.2	34558.9	35271.3	36024.9
Volume of water per capita	1.83	1.56	1.62	1.51	1.26	1.26	1.28

Statistics show that water resources have shown a sharp decline from 2021 to 2021. In 2021, the minimum value was 43661.6 million m³. The need for water has increased. However, the amount of water per capita has decreased sharply.

Figure 2: Volume of water per capita (in percent compared to 2017)²

Figure 3: Statistical indicators of the green economy in relation to the environment³

¹ Stat.uz ma'lumotlari asosida muallif tomonidan tayyorlandi

² Stat.uz ma'lumotlari asosida muallif tomonidan tayyorlandi

³ Muallif tomonidan ilmiy izlanishlar asosida tayyorlandi.

Based on the data, we can conclude that the volume of water per capita has decreased by more than 30% in 2023 compared to 2017, and this trend will continue to decrease. We think that this can determine the need for a green economy.

We need a system of statistical indicators to study and analyze the development processes of the green economy. We offer the following system of indicators.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The green economy is a driver of sustainable growth in the future of countries. In conclusion, we can say that the result of the above statistical analysis is the most optimal way for us to develop the green economy. Depletion of water resources and the deterioration of the ecological situation require a cost-effective and sustainable economy. And for the analysis and research of these processes, a system of statistical indicators expressing their tendency is necessary.

Developing a green economy directly helps nature. We can evaluate this development process with weather indicators. The amount of carbon emission, the share of renewable energy in production and energy consumption per capita are relevant for us today.

Ecosystem management is also an important factor. Through this category, the expansion or desertification of forest zones in the country and the depletion of underground water resources can be controlled.

Resource efficiency can give a chance to estimate energy productivity, material productivity, water productivity and CO₂ productivity. It leads to maximum recycling. And it is said circular economy.

By the group Chemicals and waste management we can control operations related to waste such as collection, recycling and generation.

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